

Microplastics characterization in wastewater sludge treatment line optimizing the pretreatment and the examination steps.

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Abstract

In this study, we present a novel methodology to reduce the interference of organic matter in the analysis, counting, and characterization of microplastics (MPs) in the sludge line of a wastewater treatment plant (WWTP). By tracking easily monitored laboratory variables, it was determined that colorimetry effectively monitored the oxidation state of organic matter in samples, a necessary pretreatment step for subsequent sample handling. A 3D-printed piece, adapted for a filtration system, was utilized for the first time, facilitating subsequent visual scanning and Raman spectroscopy. The proposed methodology, including the oxidation time required to decrease the colour index of the sample to 1, was applied to six samples from various points in the WWTP sludge treatment line. This colour tracking allowed us to determine if the organic matter was sufficiently oxidized so that it did not interfere with MPs analysis.

Key findings include a high presence of polyethylene in all analysed samples and a significant presence of polypropylene. The study also noted a majority presence of light MPs, although this percentage decreases as the process progresses along the sludge line. Additionally, a distribution of smaller MPs (less than 200 μm) was observed in the primary sludge liquor stream, with particles smaller than 100 μm prevalent in concentrated mixed sludge, indicating fractionation.

In conclusion, this methodology accelerates the characterization of MPs in wastewater sludge samples without compromising accuracy, contributing to the future standardization of this essential process in the growing field of MP research.

Keywords (maximum 6 in alphabetical order)

Image scanning; methodology; Microplastics; sludge; Raman, wastewater

INTRODUCTION

MPs, defined as particles smaller than 5 mm, are a significant environmental concern due to their persistence and impact on ecosystems. They originate from urban waste, industrial practices, and the breakdown of larger plastics. WWTPs are key pathways for MPs to enter aquatic environments, despite high removal efficiencies. Detection techniques like FTIR and Raman spectroscopy face challenges due to organic matter interference, making standardization crucial. Global efforts focus on mitigating MPs generation, improving waste management, and developing MP-specific removal technologies within WWTPs.

This study presents an advanced methodology to improve sludge sample processing for MPs analysis by eliminating organic matter interference. It also incorporates colorimetric monitoring to track the oxidation state of organic matter, ensuring accurate pretreatment. By optimizing processing time and adjusting the sample:H₂O₂ ratio, this approach aims to enhance the consistency and reliability of MPs analysis. Moreover, this method uses micro-Raman spectroscopy for analysis. The findings contribute to future standardization efforts and advances in MPs research.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection and optimization of the organic matter oxidation time.

The gathered samples included various types of sludge: Primary Sludge (PS), Primary Sludge Liquor (PSL), Thickened Primary Sludge (TPS), Floating Sludge (FS), Concentrated Mixed Sludge (CMS), and Digested Sludge (DS). Based on Bretas Alvim et al. (2020), an alternative processing

method using H_2O_2 in a 1:2 ratio (Sludge: H_2O_2) was proposed to eliminate organic matter.

To monitor TVS removal, four laboratory variables (turbidity, pH, conductivity, and colour) were tracked. The colorimetric coefficient was calculated using ISO 7887:2011 Method B. This methodology, widely used in water and wastewater studies, is also applicable to sewage sludge.

Design and manufacturing of a piece for improving the MPs examination.

The filtration system's initial structural design, adapted for a square area, was created using SolidWorks software (SolidWorks 2023, Dassault Systèmes). Elegoo Abs-like photopolymer resin 2.0 was selected for its modelling ease and durability. The structure was manufactured with a Mars 4 Pro 3D printer, using a layer-by-layer deposition process. Post-processing involved using the Elegoo Mercury Plus 2.0 Wash and Cure machine to enhance the final printed structure.

Procedure for MPs quantification and analysis.

All samples were vacuum filtered using the designed piece, then scanned using a Witec Raman microscope ALPHA300 M+ (Witec, Germany) with 20x magnification. A total of 5625 square photographs were taken, with autofocus performed on 26 layers for each, creating high-resolution collages. Potential polymeric fragments were selected and analysed under specific Raman conditions (633 nm laser, 0-3500 cm^{-1} range, 20 accumulations, 0.5 seconds integration time). TrueMatch Spectral Database software (Witec) implemented in the equipment was used employing Munno et al. (2020) spectral libraries of plastic particles for comparison and identification.

Figure 1. Methodology of MPs characterization process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Monitoring of easily acquired laboratory variables during the organic matter oxidation.

Turbidity, pH, and conductivity were not useful for monitoring the oxidation process, but colour was effective. The colour of the sample decreased to a value of 1 after 2 hours, remaining stable until the end of the experiment at 8 hours. This indicated that a colour value of 1 was suitable to stop oxidation before sample examination. The methodology achieved an organic matter removal of $80.2\% \pm 4.2\%$ (Hurley et al., 2018).

Figure 2. Influence of oxidation process on the evolution of colour for the sludge samples.

PrS, TPS and CMS, the colour index reached 1 after 2 hours (Figure 2), allowing MPs examination without organic matter interference. However, FS required 4 hours to reach the colour index of 1, and DS needed dilution before oxidation to achieve the same result. This approach minimized organic matter interference during MPs characterization with micro-Raman spectroscopy.

Piece for improving MPs examination by Raman.

After preliminary tests, the developed piece for improving MPs quantification was designed with dimensions of 22706 x 22706 μm (Figure 3). This allows for direct filter scanning in the Raman equipment without external manipulation, such as using tweezers, which can cause polymer fragment loss. The 3D piece significantly enhances the quantification and chemical characterization of polymers, adapting existing equipment to specific needs.

Figure 3. SolidWorks 3D designed filtration piece.

MPs material distribution in analysed samples.

The characterization of 218 polymeric fragments revealed varying distributions of polymer materials across samples (Figure 4). PE was highly prevalent in all samples, especially in PSL at 86.41%, with PP also frequently found. The database identified various polymer combinations, reflecting the common practice of mixing polymers or adding additives in manufacturing. Notably, there was a low presence of PET, contrary to many references. PU appeared significantly in TPS and FS. In CMS, polymers like Cellulose Acetate and ABS were significant. DG showed a diverse presence of species, including polyamide (6.90%), which is common in current materials but not previously abundant in earlier streams.

Figure 4. MPs chemical characterisation for every analysed sample. a) PrS; b) PSL; c) TPS; d) FS; e) CMS; f) DS.

Moreover, MPs were classified in samples by density (Table 1), showing a higher percentage of MPs with density $< 1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ in all samples. Gravity thickening increased light MPs in PSL. Besides, despite their low density, many settled in the primary sedimentation tank appearing in the TPS. Combining TPS and FS resulted in CMS with more heavy polymers. Anaerobic digestion further increased the percentage of heavy MPs while reducing light MPs.

Table 1. MPs distribution in each sample regarding their density

	$< 1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$	$> 1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$
Primary Sludge (PrS)	92.31%	7.69%
Primary Sludge Liquor (PSL)	93.20%	6.80%
Thickened Primary Sludge (TPS)	77.59%	22.41%
Floating Sludge (FS)	76.92%	23.08%
Concentrated Mixed Sludge (CMS)	67.86%	32.14%
Digested Sludge (DS)	56.90%	43.10%

Finally, Figure 5 presents a couple of examples of material polymers detected by the database. The figure includes both the Raman spectrum and images of the analysed MPs.

Figure 5. Spectra and pictures of analysed MPs. a) Polypropylene; b) Polyethylene

CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a methodology to reduce organic matter interference in the analysis of MPs in WWTP sludge. Colorimetry was used to monitor the oxidation state of organic matter, ensuring proper sample handling. A 3D-printed filtration piece facilitated visual scanning and Raman spectroscopy. The methodology was applied to six sludge samples, revealing a high presence of PE and PP. The study found that light MPs decreased along the sludge line. This approach accelerates MPs characterization in sludge without compromising accuracy, aiding future standardization efforts in MPs research.

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